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Digital model definition in CPACS format of the selected aircraft configurations

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List of abbreviations

CPACS	Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Scheme
CST	Class-Shape Transformation
DHEP	Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
LAQN	Local Air Quality and Noise
LARW	Large Aspect-Ratio Wings
LTO	Landing and Take-Off
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
SBW	Strut-Braced Wings
TBW	Truss-Braced Wings
UC3M	University Carlos III of Madrid
uID	Unique Identifier
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

The present document is a deliverable (D3.1) of Work Package 3 “Models and simulations for airframe and propulsion integration” within the EU funded project **INDIGO: INtegration and Digital demonstration of low-emission aIrcraft technoloGies and airport Operations**.

Since INDIGO incorporates various coupled multidisciplinary tools, there is a need of having a central dataset encompassing the initial aircraft geometry as well as the most significant results emanating from the diverse analysis tools. The storing of these parameters will facilitate the estimation of mass distribution arising from the design of the airframe, the installation of the engine, and the electric powertrain architecture. Moreover, they will contribute to the establishment of a singular, comprehensive definition of the aircraft structure. To accomplish this objective, it was decided to define both geometry, airframe and propulsive system for the DHEP-LARW concept using a CPACS format.

In light of the aforementioned, this document is structured as follows: the first section, after a brief introduction, is dedicated to succinctly describe general concepts utilized across the CPACS data exchange format; subsequently, there is a dedicated section that provides a description of the CPACS structure employed, emphasizing specific parameters which were appended to the current CPACS version.

2. Introduction

Integrating multidisciplinary coupled tools requires the specification of the input and output interface of each tool. It also requires the creation of a central dataset wherein the outcomes from the various tools are stored, and in this context, the initial aircraft geometry is defined. In this regard, having a common standardized central interface (Figure 1) and a universally accepted language may be advantageous not only to reduce the number of interfaces between tools, but also to mitigate errors, for instance associated with reference values, coordinate systems, or sign conventions.

With that in mind, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) has developed a common language for aircraft design denominated CPACS (Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Scheme) [1], [2]. This data format was introduced in 2005 and has been enhanced and improved ever since while being employed to support the conceptual and preliminary aircraft design of several projects.

Figure 1 – CPACS as a central interface between tools [3].

The CPACS exchange file format is implemented in XML (Extensible Markup Language), an open standard officially documented by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). It is a markup language and file format broadly employed to store, transfer, and reconstruct arbitrary data.

The CPACS framework leverages the hierarchical structure intrinsic of XML by systematically deconstructing generic components, such as an aircraft, into their respective constituent elements (Figure 2). Therefore, in this top-down approach, the level of detail in defining the aircraft progressively increases as each level's nodes are filled thereby facilitating the integration of contributions from different stakeholders and simplifying the data exchange format.

Other virtues inherent from XML include the fact that the data structure and its content are separated in different files. As a result, this enables having a detailed data structure file (XML Schema Definition – XSD), while enabling users to autonomously edit the data content through a user-friendly text editor.

Figure 2 - CPACS (version 3.4) hierarchical structure overview (adapted from [2], [3]).

CPACS related software includes the libraries TiXI and TiGL [4], [5]. The first is often used to connect a determined tool to CPACS, by translating the CPACS data to the tool specific input format and the tool results from the original output format back to the CPACS format. As a result, there is no need to modify the tools being utilized. The latter is a visualization tool utilized for displaying an aircraft stored within CPACS (e.g., Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Example of an aircraft generated by the CPACS visualization tool TIGL.

3. CPACS General Aspects

This section delves into fundamental concepts and principles which are utilized throughout the CPACS structure which are essential for ensuring a proper implementation in the referred format. As previously discussed in section 2, the utilization of a central interface among tools holds the potential to reduce errors, particularly those related to coordinate systems and units. With that in mind, the following paragraphs are devoted to describing the CPACS coordinate system and units employed for data storage.

The CPACS global coordinate system is a right-hand coordinate system utilized to define most of the aircraft data. Considering an aircraft with a null flight path angle, the CPACS “x” axis points from the nose towards the tail, the “y” axis points from the symmetry plane of the aircraft towards the right wingtip and the “z” axis points upwards (Figure 4 (a)). It is worth mentioning that the CPACS coordinate system is not the same as the body-fixed coordinate system, although in most cases they might overlap (Figure 4 (a) and (c) and illustrates the difference between the aforementioned coordinate systems). The CPACS coordinate system is also fixed with respect to the flow as illustrated in Figure 4 (b) and (d), with the angle of attack represented using a dashed yellow line. As a result, unless explicitly stated, the aerodynamic coefficients should also be stored following the CPACS global coordinate system.

CPACS also allows to define local coordinate systems, which is particularly useful to define components with respect to each other. More precisely, it is possible to define a local coordinate system with respect to the global CPACS coordinate system or with respect to the local coordinate system of another component (parent element). For example, it is possible to specify the fuselage geometry using the global coordinate system, define the wing using a local coordinate system relative to the global coordinate system, and specify the engine pylons using yet another local coordinate system, this time with reference to the wing's local coordinate system. This serves as an illustration of the adaptability and versatility of CPACS when it comes to defining the airframe.

Figure 4 – (a) Illustration of the overlap between body-fixed and CPACS coordinate systems; (b) Illustration of the CPACS coordinate systems and angle of attack; (c) Illustration of the misalignment between a body-fixed and CPACS coordinate systems; (d) Illustration of the CPACS coordinate systems and angle of attack. [3]

With respect to the units, there are no explicit attributes describing units in CPACS. Nevertheless, the general convention is that all units must be given in SI units apart from the angle which is stored in degrees (°) [3].

4. CPACS Structure

It is noteworthy that, although CPACS encompasses an exceptionally comprehensive dataset, the requirement to append supplementary data may arise based on the specific project in which it is utilized, especially when such data lacks a predefined definition within CPACS. This scenario is exemplified by INDIGO, which entails the integration of numerous disruptive technologies and introduces a DHEP-LARW concept for which not all parameters are presently available in the current version of CPACS.

To address this challenge, the CPACS development team [6] has proposed various strategies. The most straightforward solution involves utilizing the <toolspecific> node to append the missing data, thereby avoiding alterations to the CPACS structure. The second approach entails the adjustment of the schema file to identify the optimal placement for the absent data. This process may involve the creation of supplementary nodes or the addition of data to an existing one. As recommended by the CPACS development team [6], this adjustment should be carried out while adhering to the established CPACS structure, its common practices, and in consultation with the various experts contributing to the project.

In the INDIGO project, both aforementioned strategies will be employed. The CPACS structure will be modified to include parameters which are essential for the definition of the aircraft concept. In contrast, the <toolspecific> node (Figure 2) will primarily serve as a repository for the inputs and outputs generated by the tools in the course of the aircraft design and optimization process.

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With that in mind, this section is specifically dedicated to detailing the application of the CPACS structure within the context of the INDIGO project, highlighting the alterations and supplements made to the existing CPACS version (version 3.4). In the subsequent sub-sections, the presentation of the CPACS structure adheres to its hierarchical arrangement, moving from the top-level elements to the lower-level ones.

4.1. Top-Level Elements

As previously stated, the CPACS scheme follows a hierarchical structure, systematically breaking down generic components into their individual constituent elements. This fact is illustrated in Figure 2, where various levels of hierarchy are displayed. With regards to the first level, it encompasses seven distinct elements, each of which is briefly outlined in the subsequent paragraphs [3]:

- **<header>**: Within this node, details concerning the dataset's name are found, including its description, and the version of the original CPACS dataset. Additionally, it also provides information about the CPACS version of the XML schema file. While the inclusion of this last field is not mandatory, it is highly advisable, particularly since certain tools, such as TiGL, depend on this specification and may or may not function with a specific CPACS version [3].
- **<vehicles>**: This node includes two groups of elements (Figure 2):
 - Vehicle instances: comprises the nodes utilized to define an aircraft and/or a rotorcraft.
 - Pre-defined data: encompasses additional data that can be referenced within the definition of a vehicle (vehicle instances). It includes components (e.g., engines, structural elements), physical properties (e.g., materials), the mission definition and flight points.
- **<airports>**: In this node, airports are listed along with details about their locations and runway characteristics, including available runway length and position. These airports may be used for more detailed mission definitions.
- **<flights>**: contains all flight definitions. Contained data of the scheduled flight. Including arrival day and time, departure day and time of departure and references to the specified mission to the aircraft model and referenced operating airline.
- **<airlines>**: within this element, it is possible to define one or more aircraft fleets. Each fleet consists of a flight plan that specifies the aircraft models and their designated missions for flight.
- **<studies>**: contains optimization data such as definitions of design parameters and design studies for both design of experiments and optimization.
- **<toolspecific>**: this node's purpose is to store the inputs and outputs generated by the tools employed in the aircraft design process and optimization (section 4).

Since this document is focused on describing the CPACS structure relative to the definition of the airframe and propulsive system integration, the following sections are mainly centralized on the branches contained within the <vehicles> node.

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4.2. Level 2: Pre-defined Data

The pre-defined data involves a set of elements in the level 2 of the CPACS hierarchical structure (Figure 2). As previously stated, this is where a substantial portion of the data, which is referenced when defining the vehicle, is stored. As a result, this section is dedicated to providing a brief description of this set of elements.

It is important to note that, within the framework of the INDIGO project, additional elements, beyond those depicted in Figure 2, have been introduced to enhance the definition of a hybrid electric aircraft. These elements will be highlighted in the subsequent subsections.

4.2.1. Mission Definition

This section provides an overview of the structure of the mission definition in CPACS, which is located within the <performanceCases> node at level 2 of Figure 2.

Similar to the previous instance, CPACS mission definition considers a hierarchical structure, depicted in Figure 5. Every mission of the node <missions> is subdivided into <segmentBlocks>, which, in turn, consist of a series of <segments>. The previously mentioned levels within the mission definition hierarchy are also illustrated in Figure 6, which provides an example of a mission profile to exemplify the logic behind this hierarchical structure. The following paragraphs are focused on describing the different levels of the hierarchy from top to bottom:

Beginning with the <mission> node, it includes the entire route, and typically begins and ends with the taxiing of the aircraft. Moreover, it encompasses the definition of the start conditions concerning velocity, position and environmental conditions. The latter includes the definition of the atmospheric model.

Concerning the <segmentBlocks> node, it is employed for separating the mission into different parts. In the example displayed in Figure 6, the mission is divided in <segmentBlocks>, with the uIDs <designMission>, <reserves> and <endPhase>. The first part encompasses the mission from the beginning until reaching the desired destination; the <reserves> contains data relevant to the cruise to an alternate airport and the loitering phase; and the mission ends with a landing and taxi-in phase encapsulated within the <endPhase>. Using the same logic as previously explained, the uIDs are utilized for referencing and arranging the different <segmentBlocks> within their corresponding <mission> node (Figure 5).

The lowest hierarchy level is the <segment> which corresponds to a determined phase of the flight defined within the sub node <segmentType> (e.g., take-off, climb, cruise, etc...). In the example presented in Figure 6, the <segments> within each <segmentBlock> are displayed in the lowermost section of the diagram.

With the objective of helping the user to define the target mission, <segmentblocks> and <segments> encompasses sub nodes that allow the user to impose certain conditions. These include specific performance settings, such as the altitude or the Mach number, or specific end conditions, such as the range or the fuel consumed. In the case of hybrid electric design, the end condition for each <segmentBlock> or <segment> should encompass either the electric power consumption, the remaining power fraction, or the total remaining power, and either the fuel consumed, or fuel fraction,

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or remaining fuel. This holds significant importance as the calculation of electric energy requirements during the mission simulation plays an essential role in achieving design mass convergence.

Figure 5 – Illustration of the hierarchical structure to define a mission in CPACS [3].

4.2.2. Flight Points

The node referred to as <flightPoints> stores the various flight points considered. Each flight point is linked to several associated properties, including its altitude, a speed measurement, and specifications regarding the environmental conditions.

4.2.3. Profiles

In CPACS, profiles are stored based on the specific aircraft component where they are employed. To illustrate this, the elements contained within the node <profiles> are displayed in Figure 7, where, for example, the profiles utilized to define the lifting surfaces (e.g., wing, vertical tailplane) are saved within the <wingAirfoils> node.

Progressing down the hierarchy, each profile is typically defined through a three-dimensional list of points which is interpolated to generate the desired profile. Alternatively, for example, profiles could also be defined using the CST (Class-Shape Transformation) technique (for further details, readers are encouraged to refer to the CPACS documentation [3]).

It is worth emphasizing that each profile must have assigned a unique identifier (uID), which is afterwards used for referencing it during the respective component definition process. For instance, in the wing definition procedure, this identification is used to reference the respective <wingAirfoils> (Figure 7).

Figure 6 – Illustration of an example mission profile, including its breakdown into the corresponding hierarchical elements (adapted from [3]).

4.2.4. Engines

The engines are defined within the node <engines> (Figure 2). Within this node, it is possible to describe the engine's geometry, encompassing elements such as the nacelle, and it also houses engine data in the format of performance maps. This format encompasses information related to the Mach number, flight levels, mass flows through the engine, emission indices, and various other parameters. In the context of the INDIGO project, additional engine data including, for instance, the propeller power ratio will also be incorporated into CPACS version 3.4 in the form of a performance map. As with the profile definitions discussed in the previous section, each engine is allocated an uID to simplify its referencing during integration, which is performed in the <engines> node located under the <aircraft> node (Figure 2).

4.2.5. Materials

Materials properties are defined within the node <materials>, suggested by its name. Additionally, this node allows several materials to be combined to form a composite material. Following the same reasoning as applied to the definition of profiles and engines, each material is assigned a uID to

simplify its referencing during the definition of the aircraft structures within the <aircraft> node (Figure 2).

Figure 7 – Illustration of the hierarchical structure to define profiles in CPACS.

4.2.6. Energy Carriers

In CPACS version 3.4, the node <fuels> (Figure 2) stores the fuels properties. Nevertheless, due to the inclusion of a hybrid electric aircraft concept in the INDIGO project, the node name has been changed to <energyCarriers> to account for electricity as a power source as well (this alteration was suggested by the CPACS developers). This modification resulted in the establishment of two sub-nodes within <energyCarriers>, namely <chemicalEnergyCarriers> and <electricEnergyCarriers>. The former encompasses the properties of chemical power sources (essentially, what could formerly be stored within the <fuels> node). The latter involves the definition of properties for electrical power sources, specifically, the batteries.

4.2.7. System Elements

In addition to the previously mentioned alteration, a new node referred to as <systemElements> was introduced. This node encompasses descriptions of various powertrain components, including but not limited to the following: engines, propellers, electric motors, generators, batteries, and fuel cells. The INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

not limited to motors, heat exchangers, gearboxes, gas turbines and generators, all of which are indispensable for characterizing and defining INDIGO's powertrain architecture. Moreover, each system element has an assigned uID used for referencing when defining the aircraft system within the <systems> node at level 3 of CPACS hierarchical structure (Figure 2).

4.2.8. *Rotor Elements*

To define a rotor and its components, notably the hub and blades, a new node referred to as <rotorElements> has been appended to level 2 of Figure 2. It enables the definition of the number of blades and the hinge mechanism connecting the hub to the blades. The definition of the blade's outer shape follows a similar approach as that used for the lifting surfaces (refer to section 4.3.1).

4.3. Level 3: Aircraft Components Assemblies

In the context of the INDIGO project, the aircraft is defined within the <aircraft> node, whose elements may be divided in two categories: aircraft components assemblies; and additional information and analysis results (Figure 2). This section intends to provide a concise overview of the first category and highlight the adaptations made to CPACS to incorporate crucial parameters necessary for defining the aircraft concept considered in the INDIGO project.

4.3.1. *Lifting Surfaces and Fuselages*

Element <wings> encompasses all lifting surfaces, which include wings, horizontal and vertical tailplanes, canards, struts and juries (the latter two when considering SBW or TBW configurations).

Within this node, a specific lifting surface comprises multiple <sections>, each of which includes <elements> paired with an associated profile through its uID (defined in level 2 as described in section 4.2.3 and illustrated in Figure 8). The definition of wing segments is then accomplished by combining two consecutive elements as illustrated in Figure 9. Regarding the fuselage, its outer shape definition is located under the node <fuselages> and follows the same reasoning.

A more detailed description of the lifting surfaces, encompassing aspects such as control surfaces and the internal structure of the same lifting surface, can be established within the <component Segments> under the <wings> node. For further details, readers are encouraged to refer to the CPACS documentation [3].

4.3.2. *Engine Pylons*

The engine pylons are defined within the node <enginePylons> at level 3 of Figure 2. Its outer shape is defined using a similar reasoning as with the lifting surfaces and fuselages. Its position on the aircraft and load carrying structure are also defined within the aforementioned node.

Figure 8 - Illustration of the hierarchical structure to define the outer shape of a lifting surface's section in CPACS.

Figure 9 – Lifting Surface outer shape definition [3].

4.3.3. *Generic Geometry Components*

In some cases, there might be a necessity of linking geometric components to CPACS. Therefore, it is possible in the <genericGeometryComponents> node to include such geometries by linking CPACS dataset to an external file (the STEP format is recommended [3]).

4.3.4. *Engines*

The aircraft's engines are defined at the second level (refer to section 4.2.4) and referenced for a specific aircraft at the node <engines> in level 3. This node is also responsible for associating with the aircraft the desired rotor elements defined at the second level (refer to section 4.2.8).

4.3.5. *Systems*

Similar to the engines in the previous sub section, in this node, each aircraft's system component is given a specific name and it is linked to the system elements defined at the level 2 (refer to section 4.2.7). Multiple uses of the system elements are possible.

4.3.6. *System Architectures*

The system architecture is specified within a newly introduced node referred to as <systemArchitectures>. This node outlines the interconnections among the system components referenced in the node <system> (refer to section 4.3.5.). This inclusion provides the structure with the necessary adaptability to incorporate a DHEP powertrain architecture, which is essential in the context of the INDIGO project.

4.4. Level 3: Aircraft Additional Information and analysis results

As previously stated in section 4.3, the <aircraft> node elements may be divided in two categories: aircraft components assemblies; and additional information and analysis results (Figure 2). This section aims to provide a summary of the second category and emphasise the changes made to CPACS in the context of the INDIGO project.

4.4.1. Global

The <global> node (Figure 2), encompasses supplementary additional global data about the aircraft. In particular, it includes five sub nodes representing five different categories whose concise description is provided in the subsequent paragraphs:

- **Airport compatibility:** This is the repository for data related with the aircraft's compatibility with the selected airport. It includes information such as the actual take-off field length and the required take-off field length for the aircraft. For further details, readers are encouraged to refer to the CPACS documentation [3].
- **Design Range:** both actual and required design range values are located within this element.
- **Flight Envelopes:** this is where the flight envelope is specified.
- **Payload:** this is the storage location for both the actual and required payload.
- **Performance Targets:** this is where performance targets are stored, along with their corresponding required and actual values. Examples of these targets include the Mach number during cruise and the maximum operational velocity.

4.4.2. Analysis

The <analysis> node stores results produced by multiple tools that can be integrated with CPACS concerning the overall aircraft definition. The sub nodes within it store results from diverse domains, such as aeroelasticity, flight dynamics, noise, trajectories, and numerous others.

Among the aforementioned sub nodes, one is dedicated to housing the aircraft mass breakdown, which is further divided into design masses, fuel, payload, and maximum operating empty mass [3]. Design masses include overall parameters such as the maximum take-off and landing masses. The operating empty mass refers to the weight of the aircraft in a state ready for operation. It comprises the combined total of the manufacturer's empty mass (MEM) and the weight of the crew along with their associated equipment and items. According to the CPACS documentation [3], both fuel and payload sub nodes should contain maximum mass values. This means accounting for scenarios with full fuel tanks, maximum cargo load, and all passengers on board. Moreover, each of the aforementioned sub nodes comprises subcomponents encompassing the respective mass value, position, orientation, and inertia.

An additional sub node denominated <systemAnalyses> has also been appended to this specific part of the CPACS structure to address the needs of the INDIGO project. This is where the power

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breakdowns of the powertrain architectures (refer to section 4.3.6) are stored according to the different system configurations (refer to section 4.4.4).

4.4.3. *Performance Requirements*

Performance Requirements are stored within the <performanceRequirements> node. The latter is decomposed in three sub nodes housing controllability, flight performance and trim requirements.

4.4.4. *Configuration Definitions*

The node <configurations> defined in the third level of Figure 2, was replaced by a node referred to as <ConfigurationsDefinitions>. As its name suggests, it enables defining various configurations, including payload, energy and system configurations. As a result, it is deeply linked to the system architectures and system analysis elements (refer to sections 4.3.6 and 4.4.2, respectively).

In the context of the INDIGO project, near airports, the aircraft will operate using electric/SAF as part of an effort to enhance the LAQN in these areas. Therefore, this node proves to be highly useful to define different alternatives for the aircraft to operate in accordance with the project's objectives.

5. Conclusions

The EU funded INDIGO project involves various coupled multidisciplinary tools whose integration requires the creation of a central dataset wherein the inputs and outputs of the diverse tools are stored. Given this particular context, a CPACS data format, exceptionally adapted to support the conceptual and preliminary design of aircraft projects, is employed to define the aircraft in the INDIGO project.

A concise description of the CPACS data format was provided along the document. In this regard, since INDIGO will surpass the state of the art in several fields, including, though not limited to, the integration of DHEP and LARW in a non-conventional aircraft configuration, alterations and enhancements were required within the CPACS structure. These modifications, mainly related with the definition of a hybrid electric powertrain, were essentially performed by adjusting the CPACS scheme to accommodate the absent data. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy to refer that, the <toolspecific> node will be utilized in forthcoming work packages to save the inputs and outputs generated by the diverse tools involved in the aircraft design and optimization processes.

Given the early stage of the project, it is conceivable that this structure may undergo adjustments as the project progresses. Nonetheless, the structure outlined in this document will undeniably serve as the foundation for establishing a central dataset that is essential to the project's advancement.

6. References

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